

PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS OF FOOD AND SERVICE-CENTRIC ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS: INSIGHTS FROM AGRITOURISM

27

27

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Abstract

The manuscript provides a predictive analysis of the food and service sectors in the mountainous regions of Central and Eastern Europe. In recent times, agro-tourism has emerged as a primary solution for the agro-forestry-pastoral European system. Projections indicate that this sub-sector will play a pivotal role in the European food and service sectors. Data sourced from Eurostat was processed using Excel and SPSS, employing analytical models similar to those found in existing published papers.

Keywords: forecasting, mountain entrepreneurship, food and services, agro-tourism

The specific indicator for the population of active enterprises in mountain entrepreneurship within the food and accommodation sectors reveals noteworthy variations based on Eurostat data for Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries during the examined period. Specifically, Bulgaria experienced a 4.24% change, the Czech Republic exhibited an -11.73% shift, Croatia demonstrated a notable increase of 14.91%, Austria saw a decrease of -13.03%, Poland showed a positive shift of 5.27% (2016/2017), Romania displayed a growth of 9.61%, and Slovakia indicated a 7.94% increase. Over the period from 2008 to 2018, there was an overall rise in mountain entrepreneurship in CEE countries, and the forecasting model for 2050 suggests substantial growth in the coming years (refer to Figure 1).

Experts assert that agro-tourism will be the pivotal point of development for mountain entrepreneurship in the food and accommodation sectors. Agro-tourism, characterized as a multifaceted activity, currently represents an opportunity to enhance both human health and environmental well-being, contributing to the realization of the overarching goal of sustainability in rural areas. Presently, European entrepreneurial emphasis is placed on natural, organic, and bio products, integrating them across various human activities, encompassing health, and environment, all under the overarching

theme of sustainability. The imperative to instill sustainability in activities, health, and the environment within rural areas, particularly within the realm of agritourism, is a prevalent and actively pursued topic in contemporary discourse.

Fig. 3: Mountain entrepreneurship between 2008 and 2050 (statistic analysis and foercasting)

Source: Designed by authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography

Statistics

31

The mountainous rural setting provides significant opportunities for the advancement of agrotourism, a practice deemed essential in the contemporary context. The sustainability of European agrotourism signifies an integral connection between health, the rural environment, and the economic, social, and cultural facets of the constituent community. This interconnectedness exerts a multiplier effect on all domains with which agrotourism interacts. In 2017, the number of agritourism guesthouses totaled 2556 units, with a projected increase to 7113 units by 2030. The anticipated workforce engaged in agritourism is expected to reach approximately 5409 individuals, compared to 4978 persons in 2017 (Ciolac et al., 2019).

31

Evidently, the marginal difference in occupation between 2017 and 2030 is not pronounced. Consequently, within the realm of mountain entrepreneurship, the augmentation of the food and accommodation sector will not be contingent upon an upsurge in the number of individuals involved but rather on the elevation of human capital quality and the implementation of innovative initiatives in mountain rural areas.

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

European nations, particularly those in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond, should perceive rural development as an opportunity to combat poverty, ensuring the enduring sustainability of rural environments. Each economic sector - primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary - should be incentivized to devise sustainability solutions within its specific domain. Sustainability, characterized by guiding actions responsibly and harmoniously, underscores values and principles. Agrotourism emerges as an innovative solution, involving diversification strategies where farms integrate recreational and leisure activities for tourists alongside agro-forestry-pastoral endeavors. The economic and non-economic benefits of agrotourism extend to farmers, visitors, and local communities. Presently, the sustainability of mountain entrepreneurship encompasses the integration of natural, organic, and eco-friendly elements into all facets of human activities, health, and the environment (Ciolac et al., 2019).

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